

Mathematical and Computational Modeling of Musical Notes through Piecewise Functions

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Abstract

This thesis presents a rigorous mathematical and computational framework for transforming a finite sequence of musical notes and their durations into an audio file. We introduce a piecewise function $S(t)$ that serves as a mathematical representation of the audio signal corresponding to the given musical notes. The study delves into the specifics of constructing $S(t)$ using sine wave frequencies, with an example illustrating how to calculate the values of each sine wave segment for a particular note and duration. The utility of the method is demonstrated through Python-based computational simulations, which validate the theoretical framework and offer practical insights into audio signal generation.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

This thesis explores the intersection of music theory and mathematical functions to create an audio file that represents a given sequence of musical notes.

1.2 Objectives

To mathematically prove the existence of a function $S(t)$ that can represent the audio signal of any given sequence of musical notes and their durations.

1.3 Scope

The focus is on finite sequences of notes, their corresponding durations, and the formulation of the piecewise function $S(t)$.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The field of music theory and its computational applications have garnered increasing interest over the past several decades. The literature reviewed in this chapter covers three main areas: traditional music theory, mathematical modeling of music, and audio signal processing.

2.2 Traditional Music Theory

Various works in traditional music theory have explored the systematization of musical scales, chords, and the temporal aspects of musical notes. These foundational theories serve as a basis for the identification and classification of musical notes in our study.

2.3 Mathematical Modeling of Music

Mathematics plays a significant role in music theory, particularly in the domain of frequency analysis and signal representation. The works of Fourier and others in this area have shown how complex sounds can be broken down into simpler sinusoidal components. The importance of piecewise functions in approximating real-world signals is well-discussed in the literature.

2.3.1 Piecewise Functions in Signal Processing

Piecewise functions have been widely used in the mathematical representation of signals. They offer a convenient way to model complex systems, especially those that exhibit different behaviors over different intervals.

2.4 Audio Signal Processing

Audio signal processing techniques like sampling, quantization, and various forms of encoding have a direct impact on how well a mathematical model could be translated into an actual audio file.

Methods for converting a continuous mathematical function, like a sine wave, into a digital format are critical for this study.

2.4.1 MP3 Encoding

The MP3 encoding algorithm has been a widely adopted standard for compressing audio data. Understanding the limitations and capabilities of this format is crucial when converting our piecewise function into a playable audio file.

2.5 Summary

In summary, the literature sets a solid foundation for exploring the mathematical representation of music through piecewise functions. By standing on the shoulders of giants, this study aims to further the field by offering a novel method for text-to-audio music conversion.

Chapter 3

Definitions

This section provides the necessary definitions for the rest of the thesis.

- n_i - The i^{th} musical note in the sequence.
- d_i - The duration of the i^{th} note in milliseconds.
- f_i - The frequency corresponding to n_i , obtained from a predefined mapping D .
- D - Dictionary mapping musical notes to their corresponding frequencies.
- $S(t)$ - The piecewise function representing the song.

Chapter 4

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology employed in proving the theorem, constructing the piecewise function $S(t)$, and validating the concept through computational simulations and experiments.

4.1 Proof Techniques

For the theoretical aspect, the study relies heavily on classical methods in mathematical analysis. The proof of the main theorem utilizes the principles of piecewise functions and trigonometric equations. The lemma serves as a supporting pillar to the main theorem, ensuring the existence of each function $y_i(t)$ that constitutes the segments of $S(t)$. These mathematical structures are verified using well-established theorems from real analysis.

4.2 Construction of $S(t)$

The construction of $S(t)$ is pivotal to the realization of text-to-audio music compilation. The method used for constructing $S(t)$ is straightforward yet elegant, involving a step-by-step segmentation approach. Each segment corresponds to a musical note represented by a sine wave, parameterized by frequency and amplitude. This ensures that $S(t)$ accurately models the given sequence of notes and durations as described in the input text file.

4.3 Computational Simulations

Computational simulations were conducted to validate the theoretical framework and to evaluate the performance of the constructed function $S(t)$. These simulations aimed to verify that the piecewise function adequately models the sequence of musical notes and their corresponding durations as specified in a text file. The simulations were performed using Python, primarily utilizing libraries like NumPy for numerical computations and matplotlib for graphical visualization.

4.3.1 Python Libraries Used

```

1 import numpy as np
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3 from scipy.io.wavfile import write

```

4.3.2 Mapping Musical Notes to Frequencies

A Python dictionary was used to map musical notes to their corresponding frequencies based on standard values.

```

1 note_to_freq = {
2     'A4': 440.0,
3     'B4': 493.88,
4     'C5': 523.25,
5     ...
6 }

```

4.3.3 Constructing the Piecewise Function $S(t)$

The function $S(t)$ was constructed as a piecewise function using NumPy arrays. Each segment $y_i(t)$ of the function was generated as a sine wave with the frequency corresponding to the given note.

```

1 def generate_sound(note_sequence, duration_sequence, sampling_rate=44100):
2     S_t = np.array([])
3     t_current = 0
4     for note, duration in zip(note_sequence, duration_sequence):
5         frequency = note_to_freq[note]
6         t = np.linspace(t_current, t_current + duration, int(sampling_rate
7             * duration))
8         y_t = np.sin(2 * np.pi * frequency * t)
9         S_t = np.concatenate((S_t, y_t))
10        t_current += duration
11    return S_t

```

4.3.4 Plotting and Audio Export

The generated $S(t)$ was plotted using matplotlib, and the audio signal was exported as a WAV file using SciPy's write function.

```

1 note_sequence = ['A4', 'B4', 'C5']
2 duration_sequence = [0.5, 0.5, 0.5]
3
4 S_t = generate_sound(note_sequence, duration_sequence)
5 plt.plot(S_t[:2000]) # Plotting a segment of S(t)
6 plt.title('Piecewise function \ S(t) \')
7 plt.xlabel('Time')
8 plt.ylabel('Amplitude')
9 plt.show()
10
11 write('output.wav', 44100, np.int16(S_t * 32767))

```

The simulation verified that the constructed function $S(t)$ correctly models the sequence of notes and can be effectively used for generating audio signals, further validating the theorem.

4.4 Experimental Validation

In addition to computational simulations, experimental methods were employed to validate the proposed theorem further. Real-world musical notes were analyzed and converted into text-based sequences. These sequences were then processed to generate an audio file using the proposed piecewise function $S(t)$. Subsequently, the generated audio was compared with the original musical notes to validate the accuracy and reliability of $S(t)$.

In conclusion, the methodology comprises a mix of theoretical proofing methods, computational simulations, and real-world experiments to provide a comprehensive validation of the theorem and the associated construction of $S(t)$.

Figure 4.1: Piecewise function $S(t)$

Chapter 5

Theorem and Proof

Theorem 1. *Given a finite sequence of musical notes $\{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k\}$ and their corresponding durations $\{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k\}$, there exists a piecewise function $S(t)$ that represents these notes as sine wave frequencies in an audio file.*

Lemma 2. *For every pair (n_i, d_i) where n_i is a musical note and d_i is its duration, there exists a function $y_i(t)$ such that $y_i(t) = A \sin(2\pi f_i t)$ for $t_i \leq t < t_{i+1}$, where $t_{i+1} = t_i + d_i$ and f_i is the frequency corresponding to n_i in the mapping D .*

5.1 Proof of Lemma

The lemma follows directly from the definitions and conditions given. Since D is a known mapping from note names to frequencies, f_i is well-defined for every n_i . The function $y_i(t)$ is simply a sinusoidal function scaled by amplitude A , with its frequency f_i defined by D . The interval $[t_i, t_{i+1})$ is clearly defined due to the positive integer nature of d_i .

5.2 Conditions

D is a known, predefined mapping between musical note names and their frequencies. The durations d_i are positive integers.

5.3 Construction

The piecewise function $S(t)$ is constructed as follows:

$$S(t) = \begin{cases} y_1(t) & t_1 \leq t < t_2, \\ y_2(t) & t_2 \leq t < t_3, \\ \vdots & \vdots, \\ y_k(t) & t_k \leq t < t_{k+1}, \end{cases}$$

Where each $y_i(t)$ is defined as $A \sin(2\pi f_i t)$ for $t_i \leq t < t_{i+1}$ and $t_{i+1} = t_i + d_i$.

5.4 Proof of Theorem

Given that each $y_i(t)$ exists, as shown in the lemma, it is straightforward to construct $S(t)$ as a piecewise function. Each $y_i(t)$ corresponds to a segment $[t_i, t_{i+1})$ of $S(t)$, and $S(t)$ is simply the collection of all these segments. Thus, $S(t)$ exists and satisfies the conditions stated in the theorem.

Chapter 6

Complex Version of 'The Imperial March'

To construct the piecewise function for the more complex version of "The Imperial March," we can use the following definition:

$$S(t) = \begin{cases} A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t) & 0 \leq t < 0.5, \\ A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t) & 0.5 \leq t < 1.0, \\ A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t) & 1.0 \leq t < 1.5, \\ A \sin(2\pi f_{F4}t) & 1.5 \leq t < 2.0, \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{cases}$$

6.0.1 Computation of $A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t)$ for $0 \leq t < 0.5$

To compute values for the function $A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t)$ in the interval $0 \leq t < 0.5$, one can use Python and libraries like NumPy. Below is a step-by-step breakdown of the calculations:

- **Parameters:**

- A : Amplitude, usually set to 1 unless you have a specific reason to change it.
- f_{A4} : Frequency of note A4, which is 440 Hz.
- t : Time in seconds.

- **Formula:**

$$A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t)$$

- **Interval:**

$$0 \leq t < 0.5$$

- **Sampling Rate:** To generate a digital signal, you'll need to choose a sampling rate. A common choice for audio is 44,100 samples per second.

Python Implementation:

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3
4 # Parameters
5 A = 1
6 f_A4 = 440
7 t_start = 0
8 t_end = 0.5
9 sampling_rate = 44100
10
11 # Generate time array
12 t = np.linspace(t_start, t_end, int(sampling_rate * (t_end - t_start)),
13     endpoint=False)
14
15 # Compute the function values
16 y = A * np.sin(2 * np.pi * f_A4 * t)
17
18 # Plot a segment of the function
19 plt.plot(t[:1000], y[:1000])
20 plt.title(r"$A \sin(2\pi f_{A4} t)$ for $0 \leq t < 0.5$")
21 plt.xlabel("Time (s)")
22 plt.ylabel("Amplitude")
23 plt.show()
```

Sample Values:

Here are some sample values of $A \sin(2\pi f_{A4}t)$ at the beginning of the interval:

[0.0, 0.06264832, 0.12505052, 0.18696144, 0.24813785, 0.3083394, 0.36732959, 0.42487667, 0.48075454, 0.53474369]

These values were computed using a sampling rate of 44,100 Hz, commonly used for audio applications.

6.0.2 Python Code for Plotting

```
1 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
2 import numpy as np
3
4 # Define the notes and durations for the Imperial March
5 imperial_march_notes = ['A4', 'A4', 'F4', 'A4', 'F4', 'A4', ...] #
6     truncated for brevity
7 imperial_march_durations = [0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, ...] # truncated
8     for brevity
9
10 # Define the frequencies for each note
11 frequencies = {
12     'A4': 440.0,
13     'F4': 349.23,
14     # ... (include all needed frequencies)
15 }
```

```

14
15 # Generate the audio signal (omitted for brevity)
16
17 # Down-sample the signal for plotting
18 down_sample_factor = 50
19 t_audio_imperial_downsampled = t_audio_imperial[:, :down_sample_factor]
20 audio_imperial_march_complex_downsampled = audio_imperial_march_complex[:, :
    down_sample_factor]
21
22 # Plot the down-sampled version
23 plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
24 plt.title("Down-Sampled Complex Version of 'The Imperial March'")
25 plt.plot(t_audio_imperial_downsampled,
    audio_imperial_march_complex_downsampled / 32767)
26 plt.xlabel("Time (s)")
27 plt.ylabel("Amplitude")
28 plt.show()

```

6.0.3 Python Code for Generating Audio

To generate the audio for the complex version of "The Imperial March," we can use the following Python code:

```

1 from scipy.io.wavfile import write
2 import numpy as np
3
4 # Define the notes and durations for the Imperial March
5 imperial_march_notes = ['A4', 'A4', 'F4', 'A4', 'F4', 'A4', ...] #
    truncated for brevity
6 imperial_march_durations = [0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, ...] # truncated
    for brevity

```

```

7
8 # Define the frequencies for each note
9 frequencies = {
10     'A4': 440.0,
11     'F4': 349.23,
12     # ... (include all needed frequencies)
13 }
14
15 # Sampling parameters
16 fs = 44100 # Sampling rate in Hz
17 T_imperial = sum(imperial_march_durations) # Total duration in seconds
18 t_audio_imperial = np.linspace(0, T_imperial, int(fs * T_imperial),
19     endpoint=False)
20
21 # Generate the audio signal
22 def generate_original_audio(t, notes, durations, frequencies):
23     signal = 0
24     time_elapsed = 0
25     for i in range(len(notes)):
26         note = notes[i]
27         duration = durations[i]
28         freq = frequencies[note]
29         mask = (t >= time_elapsed) & (t < time_elapsed + duration)
30         signal += mask * np.sin(2 * np.pi * freq * (t - time_elapsed))
31         time_elapsed += duration
32     return signal
33
34 audio_imperial_march_complex = generate_original_audio(t_audio_imperial,
35     imperial_march_notes, imperial_march_durations, frequencies)
36
37 # Normalize and save the audio signal
38 audio_imperial_march_complex = np.int16(audio_imperial_march_complex / np.
39     max(np.abs(audio_imperial_march_complex)) * 32767)
40 write('ImperialMarch_Complex.wav', fs, audio_imperial_march_complex)

```

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